

What qualitative data would do to machine learning pipelines

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Qualitative data is often collected in the behavioral sciences, but typically not yet used in machine learning pipelines — which usually solely focus on quantitative data. In this talk, we argue that this is a missed opportunity, as qualitative data can provide additional value in several ways. Further, we will discuss under which technical and epistemic circumstances integrating qualitative data into machine learning pipelines would be feasible.

To illustrate, we present a case study showcasing how qualitative data can be incorporated in a machine learning pipeline for learning an activity recognition model from sensor data collected in a nursing home for elderly. Specifically, we suggest to inform the set-up of the search space by qualitative data from diaries written by nursing staff. Qualitative researchers would extract the information about which activities were performed by analyzing free written text. Those analyses would be used to set starting values for learning a model more efficiently and/or effectively. In technical terms, we would use an expert-informed prior distribution, in which the initial probabilities per activity are based on expert opinion.

To understand the role of the interpreter of qualitative data, and to explore if the extraction of the initial probabilities can be automated, we compare two machine learning pipelines: 1) one includes input created by qualitative researchers, as outlined above, while 2) the other one uses automated text analysis to translate the text of the diaries into probabilities.

In our comparison, we focus on how and if techniques applied to ensure rigorous qualitative research are inherited by the machine learning pipeline. Specifically, we discuss how the positionality of the researcher as well as the careful checking for consent, data provenance, and mean making with the originators might be engrained in the result of the machine learning pipeline.

In the case study, the qualitative researcher analyzing the diaries would first check if consent has been given to use them for the purpose of training in a machine learning pipeline. They might use technology to help analyze the text by keeping track of word counts or to extract topics and themes. Depending on the diaries, they might also go

back to authors of the diaries and ask for clarification or engage the authors in joint meaning making of the text. They might have written a positionality statement to clarify for themselves and for users of the outcome of the analysis how their beliefs and background affected the interpretation of the diaries. Together all those principles and techniques ensure that the resulting parameters to inform the search are set in a transparent manner.

The automated pipeline, on the other hand, would automatically create a parameter setting for the training configuration. The positionality of this process lies with the developers of the technology that chooses the parameters. In most cases, no positionality is described or acknowledged. Similarly, all of the other mentioned techniques are only used if the piece of technology and its use are designed to implement them. The automated extraction of parameters based on a text file will not adhere to these standards on its own.

Depending on the epistemic position of the researchers using and building the described machine learning pipelines, they might consider the exact process of probability extraction as irrelevant, as long as the automatically extracted input has the same or very similar values as the input extracted by a qualitative researcher. That is, the results of the trained model will be the same and the downstream interpretation and effect of the model outcome will also be the same.

If their stance is less positivist, however, and they assume that the beliefs, backgrounds, and experiences of the involved researchers and creators of technology influence scientific results, they might consider incorporating some of the techniques for rigor used in qualitative research and incorporate them into a semi-automated pipeline.

In this case, ensuring that data fitness and consent are checked and protocolled would be a first step to ensure responsible use of sources such as diary entries, notes in patient files, or video material. Further, semi-automated analysis pipelines would allow users to check interpretations with the authors of the original text. This would require a transparent interface, with a way to trace back analyses. Lastly, one could imagine creators of technology to write a positionality statement, making clear how their backgrounds informed and shaped the analysis pipeline. This would increase the transparency and accountability of such semi-automated systems.

Including some of the mentioned guardrails in semi-automated systems might make the use of qualitative data possible while respecting epistemic differences.